

Site: SPHINX TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N COLONNADE Square R16 Locus Number (3a) 8/1/80

Progress of Excavation (3a) Removed with trowel. No sign of mod. refuse as with (3). Friable alabaster, granite fragments, fairly large fragments limestone (1 large limestone slab against N edge pillar socket removed - see plan 8/1/80). At S end of (3a) (slopes down to S) nearly on bedrock bottom large maroon-purple fragment of what appears to be iron ore (haemetite?), very friable. Photoed in BW, color. (3a) Sifted through large screen sieve (just over 1mm.) // IRON ORE, MUD SPOTS, SAMPLED. NON-Limestone stone material saved in total

Locus Description Slightly more sandy, lighter tan than (3) No sign mod refuse. Compact, damp. Large irregular limestone slab embedded in (3a) at edge of pillar socket (N edge)
Limestone frags. Friable granite and alabaster frags, dolerite chips
Inclusions: possibly few small gypsum frags. mud spots, 3 small flint-chert, one possibly worked

Location in Square Sandy, E side (in E Balk), sloping from N edge pillar socket to terminate $\approx$ 21 cm short of S edge pillar socket. Extends approx 50 cm to W along N pillar socket edge

Under Locus (3) Over Locus Bedrock bottom pillar socket

Locus Dimensions 75-length, 30 cm height, 50 cm wide at N

Levels 7.89 top large limestone slab, 7.68 approx top sandy fill matrix.

Analysis of non-artifactual materials NOTE IRON ORE Frag similar to same found in N BALK R5 (NS 78) in locus of packed sand w/ concentrated limestone chips. In R16 division between (3), (3a) more interface. But possibility (3a) remains of pit fill - pit which disturbed (4) (more compact, rubble) in ancient times - The articulation between (3a)-(4) disturbed by Bardee-Hassan excavations?